

Optic Atrophy in Rural North Karnataka: A Retrospective Study of Etiological PatternsKavita Patil¹, Rajeshwari Mahantgol², Shruti Badad³, Sana Venkata Jahnavi⁴, Haritha.V⁵¹Professor and Head of the Department, Dept. of Ophthalmology, Gulbarga Institute of Medical Sciences, Kalaburagi²Associate Professor, Dept. of Ophthalmology, Gulbarga Institute of Medical Sciences, Kalaburagi³Assistant professor, Dept. of Ophthalmology, Gulbarga Institute of Medical Sciences, Kalaburagi⁴Junior resident, Dept. of Ophthalmology, Gulbarga Institute of Medical Sciences, Kalaburagi⁵Junior resident, Dept. of Ophthalmology, Gulbarga Institute of Medical Sciences, Kalaburagi

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Abstract:**Background:** Optic atrophy is an end stage result of various pathological conditions affecting the visual pathway anywhere from retina to lateral geniculate body. Ophthalmoscopically classified as primary, secondary, consecutive and glaucomatous. It is important to find the underlying etiology and treat at the earliest in order to prevent complete loss of visual function and improve quality of life.**Methodology:** A retrospective observation study included rural population of north Karnataka, who were diagnosed with optic atrophy during the period of 1 year, from July 2023 to June 2024 in Department of Ophthalmology at Gulbarga Institute of Medical Sciences, Kalaburagi.**Results:** A total of 40 patients were diagnosed with optic atrophy. Among them 16 (40%) were females and 24 (60%) were males. 3(7.50%) patients belong to the age group of <20 years, 7 (17.50%) patients to 20-40 years, 14 (35%) patients to 40-60years and 16 (40%) patients to >60years of age groups. Out of 40 optic atrophy cases 3(7.5%) had primary optic atrophy, 7(17.50%) had secondary optic atrophy, 11(27.50%) had consecutive optic atrophy and 19 (47.50%) had glaucomatous optic atrophy.**Conclusion:** Glaucoma followed by retinitis pigmentosa are most common cause of optic atrophy with severe loss of visual function among rural population of north Karnataka. Screening and awareness programme for early diagnosis of glaucoma, genetic counselling for retinitis pigmentosa with improvement in primary health care facility is recommended in order to reduce vision loss due to optic atrophy.**Keywords:** Primary optic atrophy, secondary optic atrophy, consecutive optic atrophy, glaucomatous optic atrophy.

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Introduction

Optic atrophy is an end stage result of various pathological conditions affecting the visual pathway anywhere from retina to lateral geniculate body. Optic atrophy can be congenital (autosomal dominant optic atrophy, Leber hereditary optic neuropathy) or acquired (compressive, ischemic, traumatic, toxic, inflammatory or infective). Optic atrophy is clinically characterised by presence of severe visual impairment, relative afferent pupillary defect in unilateral cases, significant reduction in colour vision and contrast sensitivity associated with central or centrocecal scotoma on visual field testing. [1,2]

Ophthalmoscopically, optic atrophy is classified into 4 types [3]

Primary optic atrophy- Characterized by chalky white pale disc with sharp well-defined margins. This occurs in absence of optic disc swelling. Conditions causing primary optic atrophy are retrobulbar neuritis, traumatic optic neuropathy, posterior ischemic optic neuropathy, compressive lesions of orbit or brain.

Secondary optic atrophy - Characterized by loss of architecture of ONH, greyish colour with blurring of disc margin associated with peripapillary sheathing of arterioles, tortuous veins and peripapillary retinochoroidal lines called Paton lines. Conditions causing secondary optic atrophy are optic neuritis, anterior ischemic optic neuropathy and papilledema.

Consecutive optic atrophy - Characterized by pale waxy disc, well defined disc margins with normal

physiological cup associated with inner retinal disease like retinitis pigmentosa, pathological myopia, retinal vascular disorders.

Glaucomatous optic atrophy - Characterized by specific mechanical and vascular signs of glaucoma like increased CD ratio, nasalisation of blood vessels, arteriolar attenuation with thinning of surrounding RNFL.

Optic atrophy results in irreversible blindness for which there is no cure available currently. The only available approach is early diagnosis and effective management of underlying condition before it causes complete dysfunctioning of optic nerve. The main aim of this study is to evaluate cases presented with optic atrophy and identify the underlying cause among rural population of north Karnataka.

Materials and Methods

It is a hospital based retrospective observational study included rural population of North Karnataka who reported between July 2023 to June 2024 in Department of Ophthalmology at Gulbarga Institute of Medical Sciences, Kalaburagi. Data of 40 patients diagnosed with optic atrophy during this period was retrieved from medical records. Demographic data including age, sex with systemic risk factors were noted. Ocular examination data, including visual acuity, colour vision, pupillary reaction, slit lamp evaluation and detailed fundus examination were collected. Neuroimaging and visual fields were advised in required cases. Type of optic atrophy and underlying cause was noted.

Results

Among 40 patients with optic atrophy, 16 (40%) were females and 24 (60%) were males. mean age of

presentation was 50.3 years with range of 5-80 years. 3 (7.50%) patients belong to the age group of <20 years, 7(17.50%) patients to 20-40 years, 14 (35%) patients to 40-60years, 16 (40%) patients to >60years of age groups.

Optic atrophy was unilateral in 29 cases (72.5%) and bilateral in 11 cases (27.5%). Among 29 unilateral cases of optic atrophy, right eye was involved in 16 (40%) cases and left eye was involved in 13(32.5%) cases. Out of 51 eyes of 40 patients with optic atrophy, 7 (13.8%) eyes had BCVA of >6/60, 14(27.5%) had CF at 5M to CF close to face, 10 (19.6%) had HM+ve, 11(21.5%) had PL+ve and 9 (17.6%) had PL-ve.

Out of 40 optic atrophy cases 3(7.5%) had primary optic atrophy, 7(17.50%) had secondary optic atrophy, 11(27.50%) had consecutive optic atrophy 19(47.50%) had glaucomatous optic atrophy.

Among 3 primary optic atrophy 1 had traumatic optic atrophy, 1 had multiple sclerosis and 1 had compressive lesion in brain (neurocytoma). Among 7 cases of secondary optic atrophy 2 cases had papilledema, 2 had optic neuritis and 3 had AION. Among 11 cases of consecutive optic atrophy, retinitis pigmentosa was seen 6cases, vascular occlusion seen in 3 cases, myopia in 1 case and chronic retinal detachment in 1case.

Among 19 glaucomatous optic atrophy patients, 10 had primary open angle glaucoma, 4 had primary angle closure glaucoma, 3 had developmental glaucoma and 2 had pseudoexfoliation glaucoma. In this present study 89.5% were above 40 years of age with more common in 6th to 7th decade.

Table1: Gender distribution

Gender	Number of cases	Percentage
Male	24	60%
Female	16	40%

Table2: Age distribution

Age group (in years)	Number of cases	Percentage
<20	3	7.5%
20-40	7	17.5%
40-60	14	35%
>60	16	40%

Table3: Laterality of optic atrophy

Laterality	Number of cases	Percentage
Unilateral Right	16	40%
Unilateral Left	13	32.5%
Bilateral	11	27.5%

Table4: BCVA at the time of presentation

BCVA	Number of eyes	Percentage
Better than 6/60	7	13.8%
CF 5M- CF CF	14	27.5%
HM+ve	10	19.6%
PL+ve	11	21.5%
PL-ve	9	17.6%
TOTAL	51	100%

Table5: Type of optic atrophy

Type of optic atrophy	Number of cases	Percentage
Primary	3	7.5%
Secondary	7	17.5%
Consecutive	11	27.5%
Glaucomatous	19	47.5%

Table6: Etiology of optic atrophy

Etiology	Number of cases	Percentage
Glaucoma	19	47.5%
Retinitis pigmentosa	6	15%
Vascular (CRAO/CRVO)	3	7.5%
AION	3	7.5%
Inflammatory	3	7.5%
Papilledema	2	5%
Compressive lesion	1	2.5%
Traumatic	1	2.5%
Pathological myopia	1	2.5%
Chronic retinal detachment	1	2.5%

Discussion

Gender Analysis: In the present study, out of 40 cases 24 were males and 16 were females. Male to female ratio is 1.5:1. Similar results are seen in Naik BS et al study [4] and Chaddah et al study [5] with male to female ratio of 1.6:1 and 1.9:1 respectively.

Age Analysis: In present study maximum number of cases belongs to the age group of >60 years (40%), followed by 40-60 years (35%), 20-40 years (17.5%) and <20years (7.5%). Mean age of presentation is 50.3 years and this result is in accordance to Naik BS et al study [4] and Bhajracharya K et al study [6] where mean age of presentation is 46.88+/- 17.04 and 53.16+/-18.1 years respectively.

Laterality of optic atrophy: In this present study optic atrophy is unilateral in 72.5% cases and bilateral in 27.5% cases. In other studies, like Naik BS et al study [4], Chaddah et al study [5] bilateral involvement of optic atrophy was more common.

Visual acuity in Optic Atrophy: In present study, out of 51 eyes of 40 patients with optic atrophy, 7 (13.8%) eyes had BCVA of >6/60, 14(27.5%) had CF at 5M to CF close to face, 10 (19.6%) had HM+ve, 11(21.5%) had PL+ve and 9 (17.6%) had PL-ve. In a study by Naik BS [4], 20.5% had BCVA of >6/60, 71.2% had BCVA of CF5M to PL+ve and 8.2% patients had PL-ve.

Our study shows more loss of visual acuity compared to above study this difference is may be because, patients of rural population are unaware of availability of resources, poor knowledge about prevention of conditions that can result severe loss of visual function.

Etiology of Optic Atrophy: In the present study, glaucoma (47.5%) is most common cause of optic atrophy followed by retinitis pigmentosa (15%), inflammatory (7.5%), AION (7.5%), vascular occlusion (7.5%), papilledema (5%), trauma (2.5%), compressive lesions (2.5%), pathological myopia (2.5%) and chronic retinal detachment (2.5%). This result is in accordance with Naik BS et al study [4] and Bhajracharya K et al study [6], where glaucoma is most common cause of optic atrophy with prevalence of 35% and 58% respectively.

Conclusion

The present study conclude that glaucoma as major cause of optic atrophy followed by retinitis pigmentosa among rural population of north Karnataka. As glaucoma is preventable cause of blindness, study implies requirement of early detection and appropriate management of glaucoma in order to prevent permanent visual loss.

Retinitis pigmentosa is genetically transmitted disorder, there is no effective treatment till now. The incidence can be reduced by genetic counselling

early screening of family members and discouraging consanguineous marriages.

Severe loss of visual function among rural population compared to other studies, emphasizing the need for targeted intervention and also highlight on to enhancement of health care facilities in rural areas.

Recommendation:

1. Integrating glaucoma screening into primary health care services.
2. Genetic counselling and screening services for retinitis pigmentosa.
3. Developing community-based eye care programmes.

List of Abbreviations

AION: Anterior ischemic optic neuropathy

BCVA: Best corrected visual acuity

CD ratio: Cup-disc ratio

CF CF: Counting finger close to face

CRAO: Central retinal artery occlusion

CRVO: Central retinal vein occlusion

HM+ve: Hand movement positive

ONH- Optic nerve head

PL+ve: Perception of light positive

PL-ve: Perception of light negative

Conflict of Interest:

There is no conflict of interest.

Financial Interest: There is no financial interest

References

1. Bayan Al Othman, MD(2024) Optic atrophy, EyeWiki. Available at: https://eyewiki.org/w/index.php?title=Optic_Atrophy&oldid=106341 (Accessed: 05 October 2024).
2. Bajracharya, K. et al. (2023) 'Profile of optic atrophy presented in the neuro-ophthalmology department of the Tertiary Eye Care Center', Asian Journal of Medical Sciences, 14(8), pp. 152–156. doi:10.3126/ajms.v14i8.52894.
3. Ahmad SS, Blair K, Kanukollu VM. Optic Atrophy. [Updated 2024 Mar 1]. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2024 Jan-. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK559130/>.
4. Naik BS, Prasoon Devi NG, Guru Prakash U, et al. Study of aetiology of optic atrophy. J. Evid. Based Med. Healthc. 2020; 7(1), 38-42. DOI: 10.18410/jebmh/2020/9.
5. Chaddah, M R; Khanna, K K; Chawla, G D. Optic atrophy (Review of 100 cases). Indian Journal of Ophthalmology 19(4):p 172-176, December 1971.
6. Bajracharya K, Gautam P, Yadav SK, et al. Epidemiology and causes of optic atrophy in general outpatient department of Lumbini eye institute. Journal of Universal College of Medical Sciences 2015;3(10):26- 29.